

Real-Time Adaptive Resource Management for High-Resolution Computer Vision over Private 5G Networks

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Abstract

The advancements in wireless networking technologies empower new opportunities and applications. However, these advanced networks are increasingly consuming more energy to provide higher performance. In line with the UN's SDGs and the need to reduce networking energy consumption, this paper presents an efficient dynamic slicing and antenna control architecture for 5G networks. The architecture was then applied to a smart port scenario, where a pre-gate is used to control the entrance of trucks into the port with the aid of a camera, with the video stream being analyzed in a datacenter to detect the presence of a truck and access its details. Experimental results showed that the architecture was able to potentially reduce the energy expenditure of the considered scenario in 2.26 MWh in a year, considering a real statistical number of trucks entering the Portuguese Sines Port in 2017. Moreover, it reduced the energy consumption of the UE, computing infrastructure, and wireless network in 9%, 23% and 14% respectively.

Keywords: Energy Efficiency, Dynamic Slicing, Smart Green Ports, Sustainable Development Goals, Green Networking, Key Value Indicators

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1. Introduction

The Fifth Generation of Mobile Networks (5G) has the potential to significantly transform many industries, with maritime ports emerging as a notable example [1]. Traditionally, the extensive scale of ports requires substantial investment in the deployment and maintenance of legacy communication networks (such as fiber optics or WiFi) leading to high Capital Expenditure (CAPEX) and Operational Expenditure (OPEX) [2] in order to fulfill not only performance, but also other stringent requirements such as isolation and availability. While fiber optics offer high bandwidth, they are prone to damage in the event of accidents, especially in active construction zones, and incur high re-investment costs when port layout changes are required. Conversely, WiFi networks, though more flexible, often provide sub-optimal communication with poor stability and limited reliability in the complex environment of ports [3].

In this context, 5G [4] technology presents a compelling alternative by minimizing the need for extensive fiber optic cabling and reducing reliance on numerous WiFi access points. When deployed in ports, 5G enables enhanced communication stability and reliability, offering greater flexibility for asset relocation and ensuring robust connectivity for mobile operations [5]. Notably, with a relatively small number of 5G antennas, ports can achieve extensive coverage efficiently and cost-effectively [6]. Furthermore, Private 5G networks [7] offer the ability of maintaining critical data and network access within the port's domain, while not being impacted by congestion or outright poor performance of public 5G networks. Therefore, Private 5G networks offer secure and reliable communications, two paramount factors in port operations. This technology has the potential to substantially boost operational efficiency and scalability within ports, transforming them into smart ports capable of supporting a wide range of advanced applications. These include real-time monitoring and control, automation of cargo handling, and improved coordination across various port operations [8]. In this context, the key advantages of 5G are its increased bandwidth for uplink throughput, which is crucial for managing high volumes of data from numerous sources, and its increased flexibility with the ability to adjust network performance to specific communication requirements while optimizing resource usage and network consumption. This increased capacity facilitates the integration of advanced technologies like AI and computer Vision systems, enabling the automation of processes such as gate and vehicle management and cargo han-

dling, thereby optimizing port operations and enhancing overall efficiency.

Despite these advancements, challenges persist, particularly concerning the management of data traffic from the high-resolution cameras (required by, e.g., computer vision enhancements added into the ports) and the associated power and data-hungry computer vision algorithms used for real-time monitoring and control at port facilities' gates and pre-gates. Recent research has explored resource management schemes for smart logistics [9, 11, 10, 12], focusing on remote execution frameworks in 5G edge and cloud environments. However, these studies often overlook crucial energy efficiency considerations. In light of the United Nations' Sustainable Development Goals (SDG), that emphasize increased energy efficiency, there is a pressing need to develop optimized resource management strategies that fully leverage the unique capabilities of 5G. Furthermore, according to [13], energy consumption constitutes between 20 to 40% of network OPEX with the telecoms industry consuming between 2 to 3% of global energy currently.

Our research paper addresses this critical gap by proposing an architecture capable of configuring both computing and 5G network resources with the goal of minimizing the energy consumption of the overall system for a given scenario, considering both domains. Unlike previous efforts [9, 11, 10, 12], which have focused primarily on computational offloading or network resource management in isolation, our approach integrates and optimizes both aspects. As such, it relies on the dynamic adjustment of computational and 5G network resources based on the real-time traffic context and application needs. To achieve this, our dual approach capitalizes on the 5G dynamic slicing and antenna control capabilities, combined with the dynamic instantiation of containerized services, aiming at enhancing port efficiency while minimizing overall power consumption and supporting sustainability objectives.

To evaluate the proposed architecture, a real world computer vision scenario was considered, where a 5G enabled camera is placed at a port's pre-gate, detecting the presence of cargo trucks and analysing its license plate for admission control (although the license plate reading was considered for this evaluation, the architecture is flexible enough to incorporate other computer vision algorithms or applications).

Furthermore, we take the analysis one step further by considering the Key Value Indicators (KVIs) [14] that are used for validating the impact of our architecture on the Key Values (KV) that it brings to smart ports. We believe that the architecture defined and developed in this work contributes

to the Environmental Sustainability KV, with the goal of reducing the energy consumption in smart ports related to networking and computing platforms while realizing a given use-case. For the use case considered in this paper, the KVIs are the reduction of the energy consumption of the 5G network as well as the reduction of the energy consumption in the computing platform, with dynamic network slicing, antenna (de)activation and service instantiation as KV enablers. Table 1 presents the KV, KVIs and KV enablers.

KV	KVI	KV Enablers
Environmental Sustainability	-Reduction of wireless network energy consumption. -Reduction of computing infrastructure energy consumption. -Reduction of UE energy consumption.	-Dynamic Network Slicing. -Dynamic Antenna (de)Activation. -Dynamic Service Deployment.

Table 1: Expected Key Value for Smart Ports with the introduction of this paper’s work

In summary, the key contributions of this paper can be listed as:

- a) Propose the use of dynamic slicing, service instantiation, and antenna control to optimize resource and energy consumption.
- b) Propose a novel architecture capable of receiving inputs from deployed applications and configure both networking and computing resources to minimize its energy consumption in a given use-case.
- c) Validate the feasibility and efficacy of the proposed architecture in a real world network for a specific port scenario.
- d) Demonstrate the benefits of adjusting network and service resource allocation based on real-time requirements to optimize energy consumption.

The remainder of this paper is structured as follows: Section 2 evaluates relevant related work and identifies its gaps. Section 3 presents a novel architecture capable of filling the gaps identified in the previous section. In contrast, Section 4 defines a test scenario where the architecture is implemented and evaluated. Section 5 presents the results of the tests conducted

on the architecture while section 6 concludes the paper with the final remarks.

2. Related Works

While a universally accepted definition of a smart port remains unsettled, UNESCAP [15] defines it as a port that autonomously manages operations and optimizes logistics flows through advanced technologies. Despite differing definitions, there is a broad consensus that the primary objectives of smart ports are to achieve economic and environmental sustainability. This involves minimizing costs associated with increasing cargo volumes, enhancing operational efficiency, and improving energy management. Central to these objectives lies the integration of real-time Intelligent Transportation System (ITS) and gate management techniques, which are crucial for enhancing economic performance and ensuring safety within port logistic operations. Notably, the application of Computer Vision algorithms and Artificial Intelligence (AI) has been emerging as a significant advancement in optimizing various facets of ITS management and smart logistics in general [16].

A key application in this area is Automatic License Plate Recognition (ALPR), which can typically include components such as image processing, vehicle detection, and license plate recognition. Most research in this context has focused primarily on image processing and text recognition. Examples include studies such as [17, 18, 19, 20], which have evaluated Computer Vision-based vehicle detection frameworks like YOLO¹ and character recognition techniques such as Optical Character Recognition (OCR), EasyOCR², and TesseractOCR³.

However, reiterating the ALPR problem while considering 5G as the underlying communication network (and its generated opportunities in modern network computing) has been overlooked in the literature. While a few recent works have focused on the broader field of 5G-based object detection and computer vision tasks leveraging 5G edge computing, they have primarily designed frameworks that execute tasks remotely in a 5G cloud or edge environment instead of local execution [9, 10, 11, 12]. In particular, research work [10] emphasizes the need to align computational resources with the

¹YOLOv5: <https://github.com/ultralytics/yolov5>

²EasyOCR: <https://github.com/JaidedAI/EasyOCR>

³TesseractOCR: <https://github.com/tesseract-ocr/tesseract>

demands of real-world computer vision tasks experimentally, demonstrating how varying computational resources impact prediction times and accuracy.

The concept of inter-slice mobility management, as used within this work, is explored in [21] and [22], where the importance of seamless transitions between slices is emphasized to maintain the connectivity and Quality of Service (QoS) required by the network devices in mobile user environments. Authors in [23] explore seamless dynamic network slicing to propose a solution for deploying PPDR scenarios over 5G in a public network without requiring constant resource allocation to the PPDR slice. In [21], the authors provide an overview of network slicing, softwarization, and virtualization techniques in 5G networks. They evaluate the current state of mobility management at a service level, highlighting research gaps and potential directions for future development, while also discussing how Software-Defined Network (SDN) and Network Function Virtualization (NFV) enable dynamic and scalable network slices to meet varying demands. Additionally, the architecture proposed in [22] uses Mobile Edge Computing (MEC) for the handovers across slices, reducing the signaling overhead on the core network. The proposed architecture improves upon traditional handover schemes, showing significant reductions in handover delay.

Recent works have also integrated energy considerations into dynamic network slicing and resource allocation. In [24], the authors introduce a slice-aware energy saving algorithm that leverages simplicial homology, a mathematical tool from algebraic topology, to analyze network coverage and connectivity, providing a novel heuristic for allocating power budgets in the RAN while satisfying diverse slice requirements. In the same vein, [25] extends Virtual Network Function Descriptors (VNFD) to include an energy consumption criteria and proposes energy-aware Service Level Agreements, allowing operators to adhere to energy consumption targets alongside traditional QoS metrics.

Moreover, deep reinforcement learning has also been used to optimize energy efficiency in network slicing, where in [26], the developed framework significantly improves energy efficiency by optimizing the slice deployments, by taking into account the network node energy consumption and the energy consumption of the network links themselves. Other slicing strategies, such as the one proposed in [27], dynamically adjust slice configurations based on elastic daytime bandwidth demands, improving energy efficiency by aligning resource allocation with temporal traffic variations.

While all the aforementioned efforts took a step towards adaptive com-

putational resource-based resource management for smart logistics, a comprehensive, experimentally validated approach that jointly optimizes computational resources, power consumption, and real-time operational efficiency in smart port logistics remains unexplored. Recent surveys [28, 29] have pointed out the potential of advanced Information and Communication Technologies (ICT) in reducing energy consumption and enhancing operations for economically viable and environmentally friendly smart port logistics. Nonetheless, there is still a gap in the literature regarding effective experimental resource schemes that utilize 5G’s key capabilities for energy and power optimization, with a need for quantitative analyses of these potentials.

Furthermore, several studies have focused on integrating energy efficiency directly into network planning and deployment strategies for port environments. For example, the authors in [30] evaluate deployment strategies for IoT networks in smart maritime ports, making the case for the use of private networks to support robust and energy-efficient operations. However, they employ a private network based on Long Term Evolution (LTE/4G), whereas this work utilizes a private 5G leveraged network. Real-world assessments, such as the one in [31], further demonstrate the feasibility of 5G private networks in port industrial areas, using detailed CAPEX and OPEX analyses to highlight their potential in digital transformation. In [32], the importance of energy-efficient communication backbones in smart ports is discussed, emphasizing sustainability as a core component of port operations as a way of offsetting their inherent environmental impact on their surroundings.

Building on all the aforementioned insights, our proposed implementation advances beyond the current state of the art by fully leveraging 5G networks to develop and implement a highly adaptive 5G-based computer vision framework for real-time pre-gate control. The framework adapts the computational resources and the 5G network resources according to the traffic context and application needs. By capitalizing on the joint dynamic slicing capabilities of the 5G environment and dynamic containerization of the computing environment, this scheme aims to support the primary objectives of smart ports by enhancing energy efficiency, reducing operational costs, and improving overall operational efficiency by enabling advanced ICT-supported port operations. Consequently, it holds the potential to make significant contributions to the economic and environmental goals of smart ports.

3. Architecture Design

Covering the gaps identified in Section 2, demands an architecture capable of efficiently managing 5G resources and minimizing power consumption, while still maintaining a level of performance capable of realizing the necessary use cases. In this sense, we propose to combine network slicing, dynamic inter-slice mobility, and cell-site antenna (de)activation to achieve an efficient way of managing resources, lowering power consumption and maintaining acceptable levels of quality of service. In 5G networks, a single cell site usually has multiple antennas, each pointing in a different direction for broad coverage, providing close to maximum link capacity. Since there is coverage superposition, there is the possibility of shutting down some of the antennas of the cell site while still providing 5G coverage to needed areas, with a tradeoff in terms of UE performance. In private 5G networks, as is the case of maritime ports, this is usually a controlled environment with multiple 5G devices that don't need extreme performance (at least not all the time). Therefore, it may be possible to shut down some of the antennas while still maintaining enough performance to realize a given function.

In light of these requirements and opportunities, the architecture presented in Figure 1 aims at providing private 5G networks with dynamic power-efficient resource management capabilities.

Figure 1: Proposed Dynamic Resource Management Architecture

This architecture considers a private 5G network in a maritime port with a private datacenter on its premises. This datacenter houses the 5G Core

network control plane and data plane (UPF) functions, and it is capable of providing applications with hardware acceleration (e.g., GPUs) if needed. The **Orchestrator** is capable of receiving application instantiation requests, allocating the necessary computing and hardware acceleration resources. We only consider the Orchestrator on this work instead of the full MANO architecture [33] since we only take advantage of its orchestration capabilities to dynamically instantiate and de-instantiate applications. The full MANO architecture is an extensive architecture that enables other additional functionalities such as the ones described in [34]. The **Slice Manager**, previously developed and presented in [35] with the capability of moving UEs between different slices with different configuration parameters, was extended in the scope of this work also to be able to receive requests to dynamically (de)activate antennas of a given cell site as well as providing information regarding which of the antennas a specific UE is connected to. In this architecture, the **Slice Manager** receives slice mobility and antenna (de)activation requests from the **Event Handler** and then communicates with the private 5G network to enforce these requests. The **Event Handler** exposes an API to applications, allowing them to request UE slice mobility and additional application instantiation. It then interacts with the orchestrator to effectively and dynamically instantiate the necessary applications and with the slice manager to move the UE between slices and (de)activate antennas according to pre-defined policies and expected application and UE performance. The following section identifies a scenario that can benefit from the introduction of this architecture.

4. Scenario Definition and Implementation Details

The next sections detail our system and its deployment scenario. The main objective of this system is to have the necessary network and compute resources at a low-energy consumption state when not in use. The detection of a new asset triggers the dynamic reconfiguration of the system to reconfigure itself and start operations in optimal performance mode. When the asset is processed, the system returns to low-energy mode, increasing its consumption efficiency.

4.1. Scenario Definition

The defined scenario is illustrated in Figure 2. The gNB refers to the 5G base station while the UPF is the main dataplane entity, responsible

for handling UE traffic. Interface N2 is the control plane interface while the N3 refers to the dataplane interface. Finally, N4 refers to the interface between the UPF and a given data network. When a UE first connects to the 5G network, its communication defaults to the Operations, Administration, and Maintenance (OAM) slice. This enables the device to receive initial configurations (such as stream parameters in case of a camera) as well as to associate it to the required slice(s). After this process, the UE is moved to the slice(s) configured by the OAM platform.

The scenario illustrates the pre-gate control in place at various maritime ports around the world. In order to optimize the admission process of trucks and goods, an automatic system can be used where computer vision is leveraged to analyse the number plate of incoming trucks (note that we are analysing the number plate of the truck only as a concrete example for the presentation of this work. Other analyses can be incorporated into this framework, such as shipping container number or damage assessment). After the number plate is recognized and the truck is authorized to enter the seaport, it receives such information in some sort of human-machine interface at the pre-gate (e.g., a screen) accompanied by the location where the truck should head next. This leverages the concept of network slicing in 5G, which is able to create several logically isolated networks sharing the same hardware without interfering with each other. The process is divided into two stages: (i) Truck Detection and (ii) Plate Analysis. The analysis framework is deployed in the local datacenter and is composed of three functions: a controller, a detection function, and an analysis function. The controller is responsible for receiving triggers from the detection and analysis functions and, in turn, interacts with the **Event Handler** described earlier for network slice (re)configuration and with the pre-gate for presenting the truck driver with information and for triggering the opening mechanism of the gate. The controller is also able to trigger the instantiation and dynamic desinstantiation of the analysis function. The Detection function receives a low-quality video stream from the camera, enough to detect the presence of the truck and, using GPU resources, will detect if there is indeed a truck present at the pre-gate. This video feed is carried via a low resource slice (see Figure 2). If a truck is detected, the detection function triggers the controller to start the Analysis stage. The analysis function will receive a high-detail video stream from the pre-gate camera (e.g., 4K) via a more resourceful slice (High-Resource Slice in Fig. 2), and it will perform a number plate analysis using GPU resources to extract the truck’s number plate. This high-detail

Figure 2: Maritime Port pre-gate control scenario

video stream is needed to analyse fine details in shipping containers, such as seal numbers and hazardous materials signs. The usage of a video stream instead of some image snapshots is advantageous since it enables the analysis algorithm to deal with reflections, positioning and/or obstructions. After retrieving this information, the controller will interact with the seaport’s central system in order to validate the truck’s number plate, used by the port system to queue trucks and provide its next location, which will then be sent to the pre-gate to be displayed and instruct the driver where to go next. After the algorithm has successfully analysed the number plate, it sends that information to the controller, which will signal the **Slice Manager** to return the camera to the low-resource slice and trigger the **Orchestrator** to desinstantiate the analysis algorithm function.

The following subsection presents the message exchange between each component of the architecture in the considered scenario.

4.2. Signalling

Figure 3 presents the procedures involved in the power-efficient mechanisms, where the messages’ numbers identify the following numbered steps:

1. In this scenario, we consider that at the beginning (runtime $t = 0s$), the Detection App is running and receiving a 360p video.

Figure 3: Maritime Port pre-gate dynamic slicing signalling exchange

2. Upon detecting the presence of a truck, the Detection App sends that information to the Gate Controller.
3. The Gate Controller processes the received information and triggers the Event Handler to deploy the Analysis App and apply the necessary network policies.
4. The Event Handler Requests the instantiation of the Analysis App to the Orchestrator, which will proceed to instantiate, configure, and obtain information regarding the readiness of the application.
5. In parallel, the Event Handler triggers the Network Slice Manager to move the UE from the low-resource slice to the high-resource one and to activate the antenna, enabling the slice to provide the necessary quality.

6. Upon receiving information that everything is ready, the Gate Controller sends a message to the Analysis app containing information regarding the video stream it should request.
7. The Analysis App then establishes a connection with the camera and starts receiving a 4K stream.
8. The Analysis App extracts the truck’s license plate and sends it to the Event Handler.
9. The Event handler triggers the Detection App to re-establish the 360p stream with the camera.
10. Connection between the Detection App and Camera is established.
11. The Gate Controller proceeds to request the de-instantiation of the Analysis App and rollback the applied network policies.
12. The Event Handler triggers the Orchestrator to de-instantiate the Analysis App, releasing its resources.
13. Finally, the Event Handler triggers the Network Manager to move the UE back to the less resourceful slice and deactivate the previously activated antenna, thus freeing network resources and reducing power consumption.

4.3. Scenario Realization

The presented scenario was implemented and tested in a real maritime port where a private 5G network was available. The private 5G network was realized using the 5GAINer’s outdoor site [36], providing a carrier grade network to serve as the basis for our tests. This network was enhanced with dynamic slicing capabilities and dynamic antenna (de)activation by using the Slice Manager, which exposes a northbound REST interface for application requests and then converts those requests into commands for the 5G network for the purposes of this deployment (the interaction with the 5G network uses proprietary interfaces and not standardized 3GPP interfaces). This Slice Manager ?? has been developed in a previous work and enhanced in the scope of this work to allow for the dynamic antenna (de)activation.

As for the private datacenter, it was realized resorting to a VM with 16 vCPUs and 8GB of RAM. The CPU model of the host where this VM runs was an AMD EPYC 7313 with a default Thermal Design Power (TDP) of 155W. This VM contains a Kubernetes cluster acting as the Orchestrator, where containers can be dynamically deployed. The VM is also connected to a GPU via PCI Passthrough for necessary hardware acceleration. The GPU

utilized for this deployment was a NVIDIA RTX4000 ADA, a datacenter graded, power efficient GPU with a TDP of 70W. The deployed containers are able to access the GPU by using the NVIDIA container toolkit. The detection, analysis, and gate controller functions were implemented using Python and packaged into containers, allowing them to be dynamically deployed in the Kubernetes cluster. More concretely, the detection service captures a 360p RTSP video feed from the camera and the frames received are processed by a real-time object detection framework (YOLOv5). The analysis service, also captures the RTSP stream from the camera, but this time, it has a resolution of 4K. It then utilizes the EasyOCR tool, a character recognition module, that identifies and extracts text from an image. Both services communicate their output to the gate controller via REST API, which triggers the Event-Handler to request the instantiation and de-instantiation of these services, slice mobility or antenna (de)activation, according to the information received.

Finally, the 5G enabled camera was realized by utilizing a generic PoE 4K camera connected to a 5G CPE (Huawei CPE Pro 2) via ethernet. This camera plus CPE bundle is hereinafter referred to as UE.

5. Results

This section presents the results of the tests conducted on the scenario presented in the previous section. The tests considered a 5G camera placed 2km away from an outdoor cell site in a Portuguese Commercial Port.

The architecture was evaluated in terms of energy consumption of the UE, outdoor cell site, VM CPU, and GPU, as well as UE uplink throughput (since the camera is streaming video). The measurement of the power consumption of the outdoor cell site and UE was obtained using a Shelly Pro EM-50⁴ (rail mountable energy meter), which advertises an accuracy of $\pm 1\%$ and $\pm 2\%$ for an electric current range between 5 to 50 A and 0 and 5 A, respectively. These metrics are then exported to a MQTT broker, allowing for their processing and storage.

The Scaphandre⁵ tool was used for the CPU power consumption and usage percentage. This tool had to be enhanced to support the PROXMOX VE in order to measure the energy consumption inside each VM as if it were

⁴Shelly Pro EM-50: <https://www.shelly.com/products/shelly-pro-em-50>

⁵Scaphandre: <https://github.com/hubblo-org/scaphandre>

a bare metal machine⁶. This tool allows for a fine measurement of power consumption at the process level, allowing us to separate the image processing processes from the rest of the machine workload. The power consumption of the GPU was obtained using the nvidia-smi⁷ tool alongside a custom developed Python application that exports the collected information to the MQTT broker. The throughput was calculated by capturing the network packets at the UE using the tcpdump tool. This capture was then exported and processed, extracting only the video stream related traffic. The processing times for the various messages exchanged in the scenario were also obtained using tcpdump to capture the traffic, which was later processed.

All experiments were repeated 10 times and the results present a 95% confidence interval.

5.1. Feasibility Assessment

Before testing the fully realized architecture in the considered scenario, some decisions had to be made for the image processing for both truck detection and license plate analysis.

5.1.1. Detection and Analysis Time

The YOLOv5 platform used for the validation supports both CPU and GPU processing, but in order to choose one of the two, a test was performed to evaluate its performance in each case. In the truck detection phase, the video stream has a resolution of 360p, and upon starting the license plate analysis, the video stream resolution increases to 4K, with both phases in the test being processed by the CPU and GPU separately in order to compare the performance of the two. Table 2 presents the time taken for the truck detection and license plate analysis using the CPU and GPU.

	CPU	GPU
Detection Time (ms)	202.68 ± 24.36	7.18 ± 2.68
Analysis Time (s)	7.53 ± 0.25	0.77 ± 0.02

Table 2: Time taken for Analysis/Detection with CPU/GPU

These results show that both the CPU and GPU are suitable for detecting the presence of a truck in an acceptable time. However, for the license plate

⁶Scaphandre Pull Request: <https://github.com/hubblo-org/scaphandre/pull/389>

⁷nvidia-smi: <https://developer.nvidia.com/system-management-interface>

analyses, the CPU takes a considerably higher amount of time to process the data, leaving the GPU as the one capable of analyzing the license plate in the least amount of time.

5.1.2. CPU vs GPU Power Consumption

A second test was performed to evaluate the power consumption and usage percentage of the CPU while processing the 360p video stream for the truck detection phase (the analysis phase was not tested for the CPU as it was discarded because of the previous test). Figure 4 presents these results.

Figure 4: Comparison between the power consumption of the CPU and GPU while processing a 360p video stream for truck detection.

Analyzing the figure, it can be seen that the CPU utilization is close to 100% while processing the 360p video, and the detection process consumes between 40 and 80 W. This consumption is higher than the consumption of the GPU (around 23 W) while processing the same data, with the added advantage of the GPU taking two orders of magnitude less time detecting the presence of a truck. This result led us to conclude that, in this particular

scenario and using this data center-graded efficient GPU, the GPU is the most suitable hardware for realizing this scenario both in terms of performance and power consumption. Even though the GPU has less power consumption, the GPU might be required for other use cases or not available at all. Therefore, depending on the available resources, selecting a CPU for the detection phase might be beneficial, even with a higher energy consumption.

5.1.3. Antenna Power Consumption

The third and last preliminary test conducted was a power consumption test of the outdoor cell site, which has three antennas pointing in different directions, as illustrated in Figure 5. For this test, a UE was placed 2km away

Figure 5: Cell site configuration with three numbered antennas. A UE was placed 2km away from the cell site in line with Antenna 1.

from the cell site with the antenna pointing at the UE disabled (Antenna 1), while the remaining two are enabled. This still provides coverage to the UE but with limited performance. The antenna pointing at the UE was then enabled, and the power consumption of the cell and UE throughout this process was measured. The iperf3 tool was used in the UE to measure the uplink throughput and Figure 6 presents the results of this test.

The results show that when one of the three antennas is disabled, the power consumption in the cell site lowers while still providing around 5Mbps of uplink throughput. The camera used for these tests requires at least 8Mbps of uplink throughput to sustain 4K video transmission, which means that in this stage, the UE is still capable of transmitting 360p video (enough for the truck detection phase), which requires a lower uplink throughput. At $t=70s$, the antenna was enabled, consuming around 250W more power but

Figure 6: UE throughput and RAN power consumption in an antenna activation scenario. At $t = 70$ s, the antenna pointing to the UE is activated, leading to an increase in the UE Uplink Throughput.

also increasing the uplink throughput of the UE to between 10 and 20 Mbps, well above the 4K video transmission threshold. These results illustrate the potential that this approach has to reduce the energy consumption of the cell site by dynamically (de)activating the antennas as needed, while also combining this feature with the network slicing capabilities of the architecture.

5.2. Scenario Evaluation

The performance of our real time adaptive resource management solution was evaluated by testing and comparing three scenarios: (i) A baseline Scenario which does not employ network slicing nor adaptive antenna management (in this scenario, the GPU is constantly receiving and processing a 4K video); (ii) A scenario without dynamic antenna (de)activation but using dynamic network slicing; and (iii) a full scenario with all the capabilities developed for this work. The following sub-section presents the results of the tests conducted with dynamic slicing and adaptive antenna management, comparing them with the baseline scenario.

5.2.1. Dynamic Slice Mobility and Adaptive Stream Management

The first test conducted on our architecture was a comparison between the UE uplink throughput. Figure 7 presents the average of the ten executed runs alongside the confidence interval.

Figure 7: UE throughput comparing baseline with considered dynamic slice mobility scenario

The scenario starts at $t=0s$, with the camera transmitting a 360p video stream to the processing service in a low-quality slice, using around 200 kbps of throughput. At $t = 16s$, a truck was detected, triggering the instantiation of the analysis service. At the same time, the dynamic network slicing mechanism is also triggered in order to move the UE from the low-quality slice to the high-quality slice, which supports 4K video transmission. The service instantiation time takes 25.1 ± 2.0 ms while the slice mobility procedure took $3.08 \pm 0.06s$. At $t = 19s$ (1), the UE was successfully moved to the high-quality slice, and the throughput rose to around 9Mbps. At $t = 21s$, the analysis of the license plate is completed, and the service triggers the architecture to move the UE back to the low-quality slice. At the same

time, no other truck is detected, dropping the throughput to around 200 kbps again at $t = 24\text{s}$ (2).

In the baseline scenario, without any of the proposed mechanisms, the UE is constantly transmitting a 4K stream, consuming around 6.5 Mbps. This peak throughput difference is due to the differential nature of the RTSP video transmission protocol, which sends the difference between the current and the previous frame instead of the full video frame. When the video stream resolution increases from 360p to 4K, there is a considerable difference between the size of the frames being transmitted, prompting more information to be transmitted.

Figure 8 presents the average power consumption of the UE in the considered scenario and compares it with the baseline scenario. The power represented for the UE (composed by the camera and the CPE) refers to the CPE power since, in the tests conducted, there is no variation in the power consumption of the camera when transmitting 360p or 4K.

Figure 8: Comparison of energy consumption in the dynamic slice mobility scenario against the baseline

The results show that the UE consumes around 0.6 W less when transmit-

ting a 360p video than the 4K video (baseline scenario). The consumption of the CPE increases slightly after the UE is moved to the high-quality slice ($t = 19\text{s}$), dropping after the license plate is analysed.

Figure 9 presents the average GPU power consumption in the same conditions identified earlier. It is possible to observe that the GPU consumes a

Figure 9: GPU power consumption comparing the dynamic slice mobility scenario against the baseline.

similar amount of power in both scenarios when extracting the license plate since it is processing the 4K video stream in both situations. However, the difference is when a 360p video is being processed, where the GPU consumes around 7W less power. The combination of these two power consumption measurements illustrates the overall power consumption difference between the baseline and the dynamic slice mobility scenario without taking into consideration the antenna (de)activation capabilities. Figure 10 presents the average combined power consumption of the UE and GPU while processing the information to detect the truck and analyse its license plate.

It can be seen that the energy consumption of both scenarios is similar during the phase of extracting the license plate. However, during the detec-

Figure 10: UE plus GPU power consumption comparing baseline with dynamic slice mobility scenario.

tion phase, there is a significant difference in power consumption between both scenarios, where the considered scenario consumes approximately 8W less while processing the 360p video and 4W less while processing the 4K video, having a reduction of 22% and 10% in power consumption, respectively.

5.2.2. *Dynamic Slice Mobility + Antenna (de)activation*

The following tests consider the introduction of dynamic antenna (de)activation in the network slicing capabilities of the architecture. Figure 11 presents the average power consumption of the outdoor cell site in the considered scenario, comparing it with the baseline scenario.

It can be seen that, between $t = 0s$ and $t = 19s$, only two antennas are active, providing enough coverage and performance for the UE to allow it to stream 360p video. At $t = 19s$, the antenna is activated, increasing the performance of the UE but also increasing the power consumption of the cell site from 1500 to 1750 W, a 250 W increase (corresponding to 15%

Figure 11: Outdoor cell power consumption comparing considered scenario against the baseline.

increase). From previous tests, we observed no correlation between the power consumption of the cell site and the uplink throughput of the UE, and this 250 W difference is exclusively due to the deactivation of one of the antennas of the cell site. After $t = 24s$, the UE is moved to the low-quality slice, and the antenna is deactivated, thus saving energy.

5.2.3. Scenario Comparison

Figure 12 presents the overall average power consumption of the three scenarios presented earlier. This comparison illustrates the difference in terms of power consumption of the three scenarios. The difference between the baseline and the dynamic slice mobility without antenna (de)activation scenario is overwhelmed by the high consumption of the outdoor cell site, which is by far the component that consumes the most power in this architecture. The scenario where the dynamic slice mobility is coupled with dynamic antenna (de)activation, on the other hand, consumes significantly less power, showcasing the advantages of employing the designed architecture in this computer

Figure 12: Overall energy consumption comparing considered scenario against baseline scenario.

vision scenario. Figure 13 presents the average weight of each component in the overall power consumption in terms of Watt-hours (Wh) (considering 60s of runtime).

In this selected run, for the baseline scenario, the UE accounted for 0.35% of the overall power consumption, the GPU for 1.70%, while the RAN accounted for 97.95% of the overall power consumption of the 5G System. In the scenario where there is no antenna (de)activation, the UE is responsible for 0.32% of the consumption, the GPU for 1.34%, while the RAN was responsible for 98.33%. Finally, in the scenario where the full architecture is employed, the UE spent 0.37% of the power, the GPU spent 1.54%, and the RAN spent 98.09%. When the full mechanism is in action, it was able to reduce the overall power consumption by 13% on average. These results lead us to conclude that our architecture was able to reduce the combined power consumption of the UE and the GPU in this scenario by 19%.

According to [37], in the year 2017, there were 58828 trucks entering the Port of Sines XXI terminal (specific to container cargo). This represents

Figure 13: Accumulated power consumption over the 60-second test of each scenario evaluated.

on average 145 trucks per day or 6 trucks per hour. With this information, we can scale our results to this real world scenario. Figure 14 presents the accumulated power consumption over the course of one year taking into consideration the number of trucks entering the port.

It is possible to observe potential savings in the order of magnitude of the Mega-Watt hour (MWh). By introducing the Dynamic Slice Mobility mechanism, we can potentially save 65 kWh over the course of one year, while the introduction of the dynamic antenna control further elevates these potential savings to 2.26 MWh for a full year with a truck volume of 58828. This represents a 15% reduction of the power consumption for the truck detection and analysis system.

Revisiting Table 1, we can complete it with the actual KVI results obtained from the experimental evaluation, where we accomplished a 14% reduction of wireless network energy consumption and a 19% reduction of computing infrastructure energy consumption. Table 3 presents each KVI with its actual value. Even though the 9% reduction in the power consumed by the

Figure 14: Accumulated power consumption over the course of one year of each scenario evaluated considering 58828 trucks entering the port.

UE does not seem impressive, we should note that these are often constrained battery powered devices, where the smallest energy reduction translates to a longer battery life.

KVI	Value
Reduction of wireless network energy consumption	14%
Reduction of computing infrastructure energy consumption	23%
Reduction of UE energy consumption	9%

Table 3: Key Value Indicators of the presented work.

6. Conclusion

This paper proposes a power-efficient architecture for private 5G networks by leveraging UE inter-slice mobility coupled with (de)activation of antennas on demand, according to the performance demanded by the use case. The

proposed architecture was evaluated using a maritime port scenario that requires the extraction of license plates of every truck arriving at the pre-gate of the Port. This scenario was divided into two phases, a truck detection and a license plate analysis phase, to leverage the proposed architecture. The proposed solution was able to reduce the overall power consumption of the system by 13% in the considered scenario by employing dynamic slice mobility and dynamic antenna (de)activation while still maintaining a performance level capable of realizing the use case. The power consumption of the antennas in the outdoor cell site proved to be several orders of magnitude higher when compared to the remaining components of the system. Moreover, considering the real statistical data of the number of trucks entering Sines Port, we scaled our results and estimate a reduction of approximately 2.26 MWh in the energy consumption used to realize the use case. The paper showcases that there is an opportunity for lowering the energy consumption of 5G networks by incorporating the proposed mechanisms, thus providing a step forward in realizing the UN’s SDGs for 2030.

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